

**Changes in Teachers' Beliefs: A Longitudinal Study of Science Teachers Engaging in
Storyline Curriculum-Based Professional Development**

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The current era of science education reform is focused on moving away from asking students to learn information about the world and the scientific process towards figuring out how natural phenomena work using similar practices that professional scientists do while building from their own experiences and ideas (Bang et al., 2012; Schwarz et al., 2017). In the United States, these ideas are most clearly laid out by the *Framework for K-12 Science Education* and the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) that came out of it (National Research Council, 2012; NGSS Lead States, 2013). Since their publication, the NGSS have been adopted or adapted by 44 states representing 71% of US students, demonstrating the influence of these reforms and their importance in the national conversation around science education (National Science Teaching Association, n.d.).

Changes in the NGSS can be characterized with four key features: that science curriculum and instruction be more phenomenon-based, three-dimensional, supportive of student epistemic agency, and coherent from the student perspective (Lowell et al., 2021). These features represent a fundamental shift in the relationship between teacher, student, and curriculum materials (Pruitt, 2014). This shift asks teachers to engage students in the social and cultural practices of science rather than having teachers primarily explain final-form knowledge to students (J. Osborne, 2014). For example, rather than using natural phenomena as “discrepant events” to highlight and correct student misconceptions, the NGSS asks teachers to use them as opportunities to provide all students with experiences around a particular event and draw out their own ideas related to it (Furtak & Penuel, 2019). Similarly, to support students’ epistemic agency, teachers must attend and respond to the ideas students bring with them to the classroom and the ways they make sense of classroom learning experiences rather than asking students to memorize canonical information without regard to their existing funds of knowledge (Miller et

al., 2018; Robertson et al., 2015; Smith et al., 1994). This work cannot be completely scripted ahead of time and requires that teachers have strong understanding of the science content, the ways students might respond to that content, and the pedagogical moves that can help students develop their understandings of the natural world (Crawford & Capps, 2018).

Given the degree of change represented by these shifts, it is not surprising, therefore, that teachers would find them hard to understand and implement (McNeill & Knight, 2013; National Research Council, 2015; Ricketts, 2014). Some have argued that this difficulty could be related to teachers' lack of knowledge of what these reforms actually mean, which could lead to relabeling traditional instructional practice as reformed rather than truly changing instruction (Capps et al., 2016; McNeill et al., 2017). In addition to teachers understanding *what* these reforms are and might look like in classrooms, however, it is also important that they *believe* that this approach to science education truly can help all students better understand the natural world. While this belief is not sufficient to implement reformed science instruction, it is necessary because teachers who do not understand and believe in instructional reforms are unlikely to implement them as intended (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2015).

Two main strategies have been used to support changes in teachers' beliefs: creating strong curriculum materials that include educative features to support teachers' learning as they implement the materials (Davis & Krajcik, 2005; Davis et al., 2017) and professional development (PD) to introduce teachers to and help them learn about the NGSS (Wilson, 2013). Recent evidence has shown that these strategies are particularly effective when combined into *curriculum-based professional development* (Lynch et al., 2019). Curriculum-based PD is

focused on teachers understanding the reforms inherent in curricular materials and developing their ability to implement those materials (Short & Hirsh, 2020; Taylor et al., 2015).

One of the biggest weaknesses in the design of PD is that it often occurs over short durations, mostly one-off workshops that do not provide teachers enough time to make meaningful changes to their own beliefs, ideas, and practices (Desimone, 2009). This is also true of research on PD, which often reports out the design or results of individual workshops over short periods of time (Borko, 2004). These designs conflict with well-accepted ideas that in order to truly change their beliefs and knowledge, teachers require significant time as well as opportunities for implementation, metacognition, and reflection (Clarke & Hollingsworth, 2002; Crawford & Capps, 2018). Similarly, not all teachers change their ideas at the same rate (Allen & Penuel, 2015), and therefore it might be helpful to understand characteristics of teachers that require more or less support in making sense of the reforms inherent in the NGSS. Therefore, we need to better understand how teachers' beliefs change over time as they engage with curriculum-based PD and teacher characteristics associated with variation in the rate of this change so that we can better design interventions that support teachers with it.

Background

In this section, we begin by articulating what we mean by teacher beliefs and how they have been defined and studied in the past. In addition, we briefly review our understanding of PD design to highlight what we currently know about effective PD and what gaps still remain in the research literature.

Teachers' Educational Beliefs

Beliefs are a well-studied psychological construct that can encompass a range of individual thoughts and opinions (Jones & Leagon, 2014; Pajares, 1992). Each person has many

different kinds of beliefs that exist together in a system, and within this system, teachers' *educational beliefs* are the set of beliefs teachers hold about education (Pajares, 1992; Rokeach, 1968). For the purposes of this study, we use Luft and colleagues' definition of teachers' educational beliefs as "personal constructs that are important to a teacher's practice, as they guide instructional decisions, influence classroom management, and impact the representation of content" (Luft et al., 2011, p. 1202). Beliefs and knowledge are inherently, and some argue inseparably, connected (Jones & Leagon, 2014; Pajares, 1992). The key feature that many have used to distinguish the two is the influence of affective and evaluative components (e.g. Nespor, 1987). Whereas both knowledge and beliefs are connected to an individual's cognition, beliefs are connected to a person's emotions and therefore can be harder to change because they involve a strong affective component (Crawford, 2007; Jones & Leagon, 2014; Nespor, 1987; Pajares, 1992).

Teachers' educational beliefs can encompass multiple different kinds of beliefs about education (Pajares, 1992). Jones and Leagon (2014) defined five different kinds of science teachers' educational beliefs: beliefs about knowledge, about science, about self, about teaching, and about students. All of these kinds of educational beliefs can be related to changes in teacher practice (Jones & Leagon, 2014). Because this study is focused on how teachers understand reform science instruction while engaging in professional development and teaching, we focus on two belief sub-constructs: teachers' beliefs about teaching and their beliefs about themselves.

Beliefs about Teaching

Past work has defined teachers' beliefs about teaching as "judgements of appropriate goals and purposes of instruction" (Voet & De Wever, 2019, p. 425). These beliefs are inherently connected to what a teacher believes about *learning* because how a teacher believes students

learn best is connected to how they choose to teach (Crawford, 2007; Jones & Leagon, 2014). In the context of this study, the most relevant beliefs about teaching are those connected to the reforms inherent in the NGSS. Primarily, the NGSS posits that students should engage in sensemaking around a natural phenomenon rather than listening to or reading, processing, and then confirming existing scientific knowledge (Schwarz et al., 2017). By sensemaking, we mean that students should be “building or revising an explanation in order to ‘figure something out’—to ascertain the mechanism underlying a phenomenon in order to resolve a gap or inconsistency in [their] understanding” (Odden & Russ, 2019, pp. 191–192). This stands in contrast to past approaches to science education that have focused on teaching students scientific vocabulary and facts and then asking them to use that information to describe the natural world (Russ & Berland, 2019). In order to effectively implement NGSS-aligned curricular materials, teachers must believe that this approach to teaching will ultimately support students’ science learning.

Beliefs about the Self: Self-Efficacy

In addition to believing that NGSS-aligned instruction is valuable for students, teachers must also believe that they are capable of implementing this kind of instructional reform. This kind of belief has often been conceptualized as self-efficacy, originally defined by Bandura (1997) as “beliefs in one’s capabilities to organize and execute the course of action” (p. 3). In other words, self-efficacy is people’s confidence in their own ability to do specific activities in particular contexts and situations (Bandura, 2006; Bong, 2006; Maddux & Gosselin, 2012). Translating this definition into the context of teachers implementing the NGSS, therefore, we consider self-efficacy to be teachers’ confidence in their ability to implement the key features of NGSS instruction as designed in the particular curricular materials they are using.

Self-efficacy has a long history of study in the literature, with a plethora of evidence connecting teacher self-efficacy with both effective classroom practices and positive psychological indicators such as job satisfaction and commitment (Zee & Koomen, 2016). Empirical work has also shown that teachers' confidence in their own abilities can be improved through experiencing PD and that change in self-efficacy can be connected to changing teacher practice (Maeng et al., 2020; Sandholtz & Ringstaff, 2014). Around the NGSS specifically, work has focused on how to improve teachers' confidence in their ability to implement various aspects of the new standards such as integrating the science ideas, practices, and crosscutting concepts. For example, Kang and colleagues (2019) found that after engaging in a professional development program consisting of workshops, coaching, and team meetings, second-grade teachers reported higher levels of self-efficacy for including the science practices in their teaching. Similarly, Lo and colleagues (2014) found that a course dedicated to NGSS instructional design helped teachers become more confident engaging their students in the scientific practice of modeling.

Studies of Professional Development

One of the most popular designs for studies of PD has been to look for correlations between one or more externally observable features of PD and increased teacher and/or student learning in order to define features of effective professional development (Kennedy, 2016). Perhaps the most well-known entry in this research tradition is the following set of five features: content-focus, active learning, coherence, duration, and collective participation (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Desimone, 2009; Garet et al., 2001; Penuel et al., 2007). As outlined by Desimone (2009), in this framework content-focused means the PD is discipline-specific and focused on teachers learning both the content they will teach and how students learn that content.

Active learning means that teachers build and make sense of the key ideas in the PD rather than simply listening to presentations about those ideas. Coherence means the messages sent by the PD align with the values and accountability structures in place in teachers' schools. Duration refers to both the total number of contact hours of the PD and the time over which those contact hours are distributed, with both needing to be "substantial." Finally, collective participation requires that multiple stakeholders from the same team or building participate together in the PD.

These features were constructed based on large-scale surveys of teachers reporting what features of PD they believed were helpful for their learning (Garet et al., 2001). In the intervening years, many studies, often written by the PD providers themselves, have used these features to establish that their PD is "well designed" and then reported some other or more specific measure to justify the program's positive impact (e.g. Greenleaf et al., 2011). While these kinds of studies are effective in providing rich portraits of particular methods of PD, they leave open questions about the variations possible in these features and how those variations might support (or not support) teacher and student learning (Borko, 2004; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2015).

Another concern with focusing on defining, describing, and quantifying "features" of effective PD is that can mask more complex questions about how teachers learn (Kennedy, 2016). For example, many interested in exploring the feature of "duration" ask how many hours of PD and/or over what period of time makes that PD "effective" for teacher learning (e.g. Yoon et al., 2007). The problem here is that while hours are quantifiable, they ignore the idea that the rate of learning is highly dependent on *what* is being learned and how it does (or does not) cohere with teachers' existing systems or structures (Allen & Penuel, 2015).

It is rare to have access to longitudinal data on teachers' learning over extended periods of time, and therefore it can be particularly powerful to use those data to understand the shape of change over time and what profiles of teacher characteristics relate to variation in this shape. For example, some may think that teachers with more teaching experience will change their beliefs more slowly because they have been inducted into a uniform "teaching culture" that values traditional approaches (Brousseau et al., 1988). On the other hand, others may argue that experience brings stronger understanding of the nuances of teaching and ability to change their thinking more quickly. By looking at how teachers' teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs change over time as they engage in curriculum-based PD, we can begin to paint a more nuanced picture of teacher learning than trying to determine how many hours is "sufficient."

Theoretical Framework

Clarke and Hollingsworth's (2002) Integrated Model of Professional Growth (IMPG) helps to conceptualize the relationship between teachers' experience in PD, their own beliefs, and their instruction. For many early designers and researchers of PD, the theory of change undergirding the work was that PD could initiate changes in teachers' thinking and beliefs, which would then lead to change in their practice, and ultimately changes in student learning (Clarke & Hollingsworth, 2002). This theory, which was relatively implicit in initial PD studies, was directly challenged by Guskey (1986), who posited that the order of outcomes was flawed. Instead, he suggested that PD leads to a change in teacher practices, which results in improved learning outcomes, and ultimately a change in teacher's beliefs about learning. What both Guskey and the earlier theory of change he was critiquing had in common, therefore, was a view of teacher learning as a linear series of changes resulting from engagement in PD.

The IMPG came as a growth from these theories as well as developing understandings of teacher learning as both the development of multiple kinds of knowledge (Shulman, 1987) and as situated in an ecosystem of interactions between individuals and their contexts (Greeno, 1997). Drawing on these ideas, the IMPG posits that change takes place in four different domains: the external domain, meaning the external stimuli or sources of information provided to a teacher; the personal domain, meaning the teacher's knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes; the domain of practice, meaning what the teacher actually does in the classroom; and the domain of consequence, meaning the outcomes the teacher values, such as student performance (Clarke & Hollingsworth, 2002). Figure 1 below outlines this model. The arrows represent the two mediating processes that support change for teachers: enactment and reflection. For example, as teachers enact new curricular materials introduced in PD, they may modify their practice, connecting the external and practice domains, as represented by arrow 1 in Figure 1. As well, teachers may reflect on the ideas introduced in PD to influence their beliefs or knowledge (arrow 2) and/or reflection on their enactment may influence those beliefs (arrow 3). The two key ideas here are that these processes of reflection and enactment support change and that change is not necessarily linear or uniform, but rather can cyclically build across multiple domains in ways that are specific to individuals and learning situations.

[Insert Figure 1]

Research Questions

Given the role of teachers' teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs in influencing both what they learn from PD and how they ultimately implement those ideas in the classroom, we investigated how these constructs changed over time as a group of science teachers engaged in curriculum-based PD. Specifically, we asked 1) how do teachers' teaching beliefs and self-

efficacy beliefs change over the course of learning about and implementing new science curricula? and 2) what teacher characteristics predict differences in initial teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs and their change over time?

Methods

To answer these research questions, we analyzed survey results from a group of teachers who participated in four rounds of curriculum-based PD from mid-2018 through early 2020. This curriculum-based PD took place in the context of the field test for the OpenSciEd middle school science curriculum, so we begin by describing the curriculum and PD context before discussing the participants, measures, and analyses.

Context

OpenSciEd is a non-profit organization that designs reform-oriented science curricula and releases the curricular materials and curriculum-based PD as open educational resources (OpenSciEd, 2020). It began in 2018 with middle school (6th, 7th, and 8th grade) curriculum development. Each unit went through a multistep development process: after being written, units were field tested in classrooms in the 10 OpenSciEd partner states, externally reviewed by the NextGenScience Peer Review Panel, and revised before public release (Edelson et al., 2021). The curriculum was designed such that the middle school scope and sequence would address all of the relevant NGSS performance expectations across life, physical, and earth science as well as engineering, technology, and applications of science (Edelson et al., 2021). As a sign of their alignment with the NGSS, 15 of the 18 middle school units have been awarded the NGSS Design Badge, a marker that the materials are high quality and designed for the NGSS (NextGenScience, 2022).

The OpenSciEd curricular materials are designed to take a storyline approach, which means they are centered around students figuring out a complex anchoring phenomenon and each lesson is motivated by questions students co-construct with the teacher about that phenomenon (Reiser et al., 2021; Zivic et al., 2018). For example, the eighth-grade unit on sound begins with students watching a video of music playing from a car causing windows on the other end of a parking lot to move, which leads to questions about how sound is generated and travels. As a result of these questions, the class then investigates various instruments and sound makers to determine how sound is related to vibration before investigating how sound moves and transfers energy through air (OpenSciEd, 2019). The idea for this approach is that even though the teacher has an idea of where the class might go next, the steps are motivated by student questions about the phenomenon rather than a list of topics or sections stipulated by the textbook (Reiser et al., 2021). This curricular approach is relatively novel, and therefore most teachers need support in effectively implementing it. To provide that support, OpenSciEd also has designed curriculum-based PD to align with the curricular materials it releases (Edelson et al., 2021; McNeill & Reiser, 2018).

Curriculum-Based Professional Development Context

This study focuses on surveys taken after the curriculum-based PD given during the field test of each OpenSciEd unit. PD sessions were designed and implemented as new units were field tested, which happened every six months beginning in June 2018 and lasting until January 2021, totaling six rounds of PD and curriculum in three years. Because the last two rounds were substantially disrupted by the COVID pandemic, we focus on the first four rounds of PD, which were field tested in June 2018, January 2019, June 2019, and January 2020. The first round was a four-day introduction to OpenSciEd, the storyline approach, and the particular curricular unit

teachers would be implementing (which was different for 6th, 7th, and 8th grade teachers). Subsequent rounds were either 2 or 2.5 days long and included a focus on a central topic and an introduction to the new curricular unit. These PD topics were determined based on feedback from teachers after past rounds. They were: identifying and reflecting on key elements of OpenSciEd (round 2), supporting equitable sensemaking through class discussion (round 3), and using assessment to support sensemaking (round 4).

In order for PD to be effective, it is important that its design be guided by evidence-based design principles; in this case, the PD was guided by four such principles: supporting teachers in taking the student perspective, analyzing images of classroom instruction, examining contrasting cases of curriculum or instruction, and engaging in cycles of enactment and reflection (McNeill et al., 2022). Taking on the student perspective is important because it helps teachers to empathize with how students might think and feel when engaging in storyline curricula (Lowell & McNeill, 2020). This principle informed the decision to ask teachers to experience lessons from the curriculum as a student. Analyzing images of classroom instruction was done by using classroom video to illustrate key moments from the curriculum. This work is important because it allows teachers to see key instructional moves in use and consider how they might apply those ideas in their own practice, (Roth et al., 2019; Taylor et al., 2017). Asking teachers to examine contrasting curricular cases can help to illustrate specific strategies in context and support teachers to develop general ideas from particular examples (Kolodner et al., 2003). This principle informed the decision to read vignettes that contrasted traditional and OpenSciEd approaches to instruction. Finally, embedding PD in cycles of enactment and reflection helps situate teachers' learning in their own practice and gives them opportunities to reflect on their experiences teaching and use that to develop their understanding of key curricular reforms (Ball & Cohen,

1999; Krajcik et al., 1994). This principle informed the overall structure of multiple rounds of PD taking place over time while teachers enacted new units between each round.

Based on these four design principles, the PD sessions for each round had a similar structure: each day began with participants from across all three grade levels working together to consider the problem of practice through examination of classroom video, reflection on their own practice and/or discussion of vignettes of instruction or student work. The participants then split into grade-level groups to concentrate on their particular unit by engaging in key lessons from the student perspective and reflecting on the unit storyline and design. Finally, the participants ended the day coming back together to synthesize their learning across grade levels. Table 1 gives a summary of the focus and activities of the first four rounds of PD.

[Insert Table 1]

Participants

The OpenSciEd units and accompanying PD sessions were field tested in 10 partner states that represent both geographic and demographic diversity: California, Iowa, Louisiana, Massachusetts, Michigan, New Jersey, New Mexico, Oklahoma, Rhode Island, and Washington. In order to facilitate efficient delivery of each round of PD across all 10 states, a cadre of PD facilitators was trained centrally before each round of the field test.

Each state recruited a cohort of teachers to field test both the PD and curricular materials. The size of those cohorts ranged from 14 to 50 teachers, although each state experienced some attrition throughout the field test and some added new teachers part way through the field test. The sample for this study is the field test teachers who engaged in at least one PD workshop, which totaled 322 participants; specifically, the sample was 209 teachers after the first PD, 197 after the second, 173 after the third, and 162 after the fourth. In terms of gender and teaching

experience, the sample is roughly similar to the national population of middle school teachers. Among the participants, 72% identified as a woman, and the average years of teacher experience was 12.2 (s.d. = 8.26) with a range of 0 to 39. Nationally, 72.1% of middle school teachers identify as women and the average years of experience of middle school teachers is 13.9 (Taie & Goldring, 2020). In terms of race, 77% of the participants identified as White, 6% as Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander, 3% as Black, 2% as Asian or Asian American, 2% as American Indian or Native Alaskan, 1% as Latinx, 4% as multiracial, and 6% declined to racially identify. Our sample is approximately similar to the national population of middle school teachers who identify as White (79.2%) and Asian or Asian American (1.9%). Indigenous and multiracial teachers are overrepresented in our sample; nationally 0.1% of middle school teachers identify as Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander, 0.5% identify as American Indian/Alaska Native, and 1.6% identify as multiracial. Nationally, 7.7% of middle school teachers identify as Black and 8.9% identify as Latinx, meaning Black and Latinx teachers are underrepresented in our sample compared to the national population of middle school teachers (Taie & Goldring, 2020).

Measures

Before the first PD, participants took a survey asking about their background and teaching context, their teaching beliefs, and their self-efficacy for implementing the OpenSciEd curricular approach. After each round of PD, they took a survey asking about their teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs, and their perception of the value of the various PD activities. This study draws from five surveys taken across the first two years of the project: the pre-PD, post-PD1, post-PD2, post-PD3, and post-PD4 surveys.

Outcome Variables: Traditional Teaching Beliefs and Storyline Implementation Self-Efficacy

To assess the teachers' teaching beliefs, the pre-PD, PD1, and PD3 surveys included a set of items initially reported by Reiser and colleagues (2017). Some of the items in the set were initially asked by Banilower and colleagues in the 2012 *National Survey of Science and Mathematics Education* (2013) while others were originally written by Reiser and colleagues (2017). Eight of these items (items 1-8 in Table 2) were a set of items that Reiser and colleagues called "beliefs about traditional instruction" because they represent ideas that teachers might hold that run counter to intended instructional reforms, such as a focus on students memorizing vocabulary and engaging in "hands on" investigations solely in order to increase engagement (Furtak & Penuel, 2019). The other two (items 9 and 10) were from a set Reiser and colleagues (2017) called "beliefs about using student ideas in instruction." Participants were asked to rate their level of agreement with each belief item on a six-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." These items were not given in every survey because other items assessing different constructs were included in the PD2 and PD4 surveys and there were concerns about survey length. We recognize that the data would be stronger if these items had been given at every time point.

The self-efficacy items were based on items used by Reiser and colleagues (2017). They were designed to determine the degree to which teachers believed they could implement the routines of storyline curricula that aligned with NGSS. The items in this survey were written to target the specific components of the OpenSciEd curricular approach, asking teachers to rate their confidence on a five-point Likert scale ranging from "very unsure" to "very confident." Table 2 shows all of the teaching belief and self-efficacy belief items participants answered.

Validity refers to whether an instrument actually measures what it claims to measure (Field, 2013). Evidence for validity includes that the instrument has been used in past studies to measure the same construct being measured in this study. Reiser et al. (2017) designed this instrument to measure science teachers' traditional teaching beliefs and storyline curriculum implementation self-efficacy. As part of that design, they used some items from Banilower and colleagues (2013), who also designed their instrument to measure science teachers' traditional teaching beliefs. Therefore, based on the past use of this instrument by both Reiser and colleagues (2017) and Banilower and colleagues (2013), we concluded this was a valid instrument to measure teachers' traditional teaching beliefs and self-efficacy for implementing storyline curricula.

[Insert Table 2]

We performed an exploratory factor analysis on the teaching belief and self-efficacy belief items separately at each time point to determine how those variables were behaving. For the teaching belief items, there was one factor with an eigenvalue higher than 1 at each time point, which consisted of items 1-8 from Table 2. The remaining two items (9 and 10) did not load onto this factor and were therefore excluded from analysis. This aligns with what Reiser and colleagues (2017) found about these items; items 1-8 loaded onto one construct and 9 and 10 were part of a separate construct. All five self-efficacy belief items loaded onto one factor at each time point. Based on this analysis, we named these two factors "traditional teaching beliefs" and "storyline implementation self-efficacy."

When doing factor analysis, reliability testing is an important step to ensure the identified factors can be interpreted consistently across many different situations; in other words, two people who are the same on the factor measured should receive the same score (Field, 2013). The

most common way to test reliability is Cronbach's Alpha, which is a measure of the internal consistency, and therefore reliability, of a factor (Field, 2013). We tested the reliability of the two identified factors by calculating Cronbach's alpha at each time point, as shown in Table 3. For every time point, the reliability was above 0.7, which is generally considered acceptable, and all but one reliability measure was above 0.8, which is generally considered a benchmark of good reliability (Field, 2013; Netemeyer et al., 2003). Reiser and colleagues (2017) found the reliability of these constructs had a similar range. Therefore, we concluded that this was a reliable measure of traditional teaching beliefs and storyline implementation self-efficacy.

[Insert Table 3]

Based on the factor analysis, we created a total score for each factor by summing the scores of each item in the factor, a common method for creating factor scores from Likert-type items (Netemeyer et al., 2003). Because the eight teaching belief items each had six response options, the total score had a theoretical range of 8-48, with 8 representing lowest levels of traditional beliefs and 48 representing the highest levels. Similarly, the five self-efficacy items had five response options each, meaning the storyline implementation self-efficacy total score had a theoretical range of 5-25, with 5 representing the lowest possible self-efficacy and 25 the highest. Table 4 shows the descriptive statistics for the outcome variables at each time point.

[Insert Table 4]

Predictor Variables

We used two sets of predictor variables in this study: a set of items asking teachers to rate how valuable they found various PD activities and a set of teacher characteristics items. Below we discuss these items in more depth and provide descriptive statistics for each.

Value of PD Activities Items. Each post-PD survey asked teachers to rate on a 3-point Likert scale the degree to which they found specific activities from the PD valuable (i.e., 1 = not at all valuable, 2 = somewhat valuable, and 3 = very valuable). This 3-point scale was chosen to reduce the cognitive demand for teachers as they filled out the survey. Some of these items were consistent across all PD rounds and others asked about activities that were unique to each round. We analyzed the three items that were identical for all four PD sessions because they represented activities that happened in each workshop. These items were: “engaging in the anchoring phenomenon for your specific unit,” “conducting investigations from the students’ perspective for your specific unit,” and “building the storyline for your specific unit.”

For each time point, we began by conducting an exploratory factor analysis and found that the three items each loaded onto one factor. Given that these activities were different, we interpreted this factor to represent how valuable the teacher found the PD in general. We created a composite score for each time point by summing the scores from the three items. Although these items were asked across time, we were unsure if participants’ responses changed over time, so we then constructed an unconditional linear growth model of this value construct using HLM 8 software (Raudenbush et al., 2019). We found that the amount teachers valued the PD activities did not vary significantly over time ($\beta = -0.04$, $p = .108$), and therefore concluded that teachers’ value of PD activities could be modeled by a between-person variable. We constructed this variable by averaging the summed PD value scores for each participant across the four time points. Descriptive statistics for this final variable are shown in Table 5.

Teacher Background Characteristics. We included the following teacher characteristics as potential covariates: participants’ gender identity, race, years of teaching experience, percent of career spent teaching middle school science, minutes per week they teach

science, past amount of NGSS-aligned PD, and how recently their state had adopted the NGSS or standards based on the NGSS. For gender, the sample was heavily weighted towards women, so we constructed a dummy variable with woman as the reference category and compared that to anyone who did not identify as a woman. Because the sample was so predominantly White, there was not enough variability to make meaningful comparisons between any other racial categories. Therefore, for race we constructed one dummy variable comparing participants who identified as White and those who did not identify as White. The pre-PD survey asked teachers how many years of teaching experience they had prior to the first PD as well as how many years they had taught middle school science. In order to avoid collinearity between these two variables, we calculated the percent of each participant's career that had been spent teaching middle school. The pre-PD survey asked teachers both how many days per week they taught science and how many minutes each class period was; we multiplied these two values together to find how many minutes per week they taught science class. Teachers self-reported the number of hours of NGSS-aligned PD they had experienced before the first round of PD. In order to facilitate interpretation of this number, we divided it by eight to represent a standard eight-hour "day" of PD. In order to determine how recently each participant's state had adopted NGSS, we referenced each state's standards adoption timeline and constructed a variable representing how many years before the first round of PD the state had adopted NGSS.

Once we constructed all relevant items, we used a boxplot to find outliers of greater than three standard deviations away from the mean (J. W. Osborne, 2010). We inspected each outlier to determine if it was likely due to a data input error and addressed each through either correcting, truncating, or deleting (Aguinis et al., 2013). For example, one teacher wrote they taught 200-minute classes 5 days a week, which was likely an input error because a second

teacher at the same school taught 45-minute classes, so we corrected the entries to match. On the other hand, another teacher wrote they taught 60-minute classes 0 days a week; because no other teacher from the sample taught in that same school, we deleted that entry for that variable. Four participants wrote that they had experienced over 1000 hours of NGSS-aligned PD by 2018, which would represent 125 or more days of PD in the five years between the release of the NGSS in 2013 and the time of data collection. Given the large amount of time this represents, we truncated each of these entries to a high but still realistic number, which is an acceptable way to handle these kinds of outliers (Aguinis et al., 2013). We chose to truncate these entries to 75 days, which represents 15 8-hour days of PD per year between 2013 and 2018. Table 5 shows the descriptive statistics of all of the predictor items after data cleaning.

[Insert Table 5]

Data Analyses

Because the outcome variables were measured at a different number of time points (three for traditional teaching beliefs, five for storyline implementation self-efficacy), we investigated changes in each construct separately. We began by graphing the average change in each construct over the time studied, which is a helpful preliminary step when working with longitudinal data to understand their overall shape (Singer & Willett, 2003). In order to explain variations in initial status and change over time, we constructed a set of two-level hierarchical growth models, with time points nested within individuals (Hedeker & Gibbons, 2006; Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002). This approach is necessary because hierarchical linear modeling (HLM) can account for self-correlation when multiple data points are collected from the same individuals over time (Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002). In addition, it is robust to individuals who do not have a full set of data points over time, a particularly common problem in longitudinal studies (Hedeker & Gibbons, 2006). This approach can also take into account that individuals

had different amounts of experience with the PD, with some entering at later rounds than others. A common concern with modeling growth over time is assuming linear growth when change may in fact be curvilinear. To address this concern, we added higher order variables of time to determine if growth was curvilinear (Singer & Willett, 2003).

For each outcome variable, we began by constructing an unconditional, quadratic growth model with random intercept and slopes. For both models, we found that the variability in the slope for Time² was not significantly different from zero. Therefore, we fixed that slope and our initial unconditional models took the following form:

$$\text{Level 1: } Y_{ti} = \pi_{0i} + \pi_{1i}(\text{Time}) + \pi_{2i}(\text{Time}^2) + e_{ti}$$

$$\text{Level 2: } \pi_{0i} = \beta_{00} + r_{0i}$$

$$\pi_{1i} = \beta_{10} + r_{1i}$$

$$\pi_{2i} = \beta_{20}$$

In this model, Y_{ti} represents the outcome variable (traditional teaching beliefs or storyline implementation self-efficacy) at time t for individual i . The level 1 intercept (π_{0i}) represents the predicted value of the outcome for individual i at time 0. The level 1 coefficient for time (π_{1i}) represents the predicted change in the outcome variable for a 1-unit change in time. The coefficient for time² (π_{2i}) represents changes in the rate of change of the outcome variable over time. Because we were interested in how teaching and self-efficacy beliefs change after engaging in rounds of PD and curriculum enactment, we coded the pre-PD survey at time 0 and each subsequent PD as time 1-4.

Our goal was to construct the most parsimonious model that could explain differences in traditional teaching beliefs and storyline implementation self-efficacy. Therefore, we employed a forward-selection model building process in which we added the level-2 predictor variables into

the model one at a time and assessed the significance of each predictor. Predictors whose coefficients were significantly different from zero at the level of $\alpha < .05$ were retained and those that were non-significant were removed. We also monitored the deviance, reliability, and intraclass correlation coefficient to track the overall quality of the model over time. When we arrived at our final model, we used the variance of the final and unconditional models to calculate the amount of variance the model explained for each random-effects predictor (Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002).

Results

Based on a set of teacher surveys, we tracked how teachers' traditional teaching beliefs and storyline implementation self-efficacy changed over time. For each construct, we began by graphing the mean scores across all of the teachers over time, which showed significant changes that began to level off over time. We then constructed a longitudinal two-level HLM model for both teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs to identify teacher characteristics that helped explain differences in these outcomes. Teachers with more teaching experience, more past PD, and who found the PD activities more valuable were less likely to agree with statements representing traditional teaching beliefs. Similarly, teachers with more past PD were more likely to have higher storyline implementation self-efficacy and teachers who found the PD more valuable showed quicker increase in self-efficacy.

Teachers' Traditional Teaching Beliefs

Teachers' traditional teaching beliefs showed significant change after the initial round of PD that leveled off over time. Before beginning any PD, the average traditional belief score across all teachers was 22.75 points, which decreased to 17.64 points by the final measured time point after the third round of PD. This corresponds to a shift in average rating from around

“slightly disagree” to items like “Teachers should provide students with the outcome of an activity in advance so students know they are on the right track as they do the activity” on the pre-PD survey towards “moderately disagree” on the final survey (Table 2 includes all of the teaching belief items). Figure 2 is a graph of this change over time, demonstrating that the significant decrease in traditional beliefs occurred between the pre-PD survey and after the first round of PD with no significant change between rounds 1 and 3. The 95% confidence intervals around the mean, shown in Table 4, confirm that traditional beliefs decreased significantly between time point 0 and 1 but did not show significant change between time points 1 and 3 (note that the belief items were not asked after PD 2 and 4).

[Insert Figure 2]

As an overall group, teachers moved away from traditional beliefs after round 1 and stayed at about that same level through subsequent rounds. The problem with looking only at means, however, is it can mask complexity in the sample. In order to see if teachers showed this shift equally and which teacher characteristics predict differences in this shift between teachers, we constructed a two-level longitudinal model (Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002). Table 6 includes both the unconditional and final model. The within-individual results confirm our conclusion for research question 1 that there was a significant decrease in levels of traditional teaching beliefs over time but that change was not linear; the rate of decrease of traditional beliefs slowed over time. The results at the between-individual level helps to answer research question 2, providing information about which teacher characteristics predict differences in traditional teaching beliefs. Teachers who had more experience teaching, had experienced more aligned PD, and who placed more value on the PD activities were more likely to disagree with the traditional teaching beliefs statements. None of the variables tested were significant predictors in differences over time.

[Insert Table 6]

The percent of variance the model explained at each level helps to determine how well this model explains differences between teachers. In comparison to the unconditional model, the final model explained 20% of the variance in initial levels of traditional teaching beliefs and 1% or less of the variance in change over time or within people, which is expected given that there were no significant predictors within individuals or for change over time.

Teachers' Storyline Implementation Self-Efficacy

The pattern for storyline implementation self-efficacy was similar to the one for traditional teaching beliefs: self-efficacy increased over the early rounds of PD and then leveled off over time. Initially, the average self-efficacy score was 19.50, which corresponded with a rating of “somewhat confident” in response to items like “help students use science practices to figure out pieces of core science ideas” (see all self-efficacy items in Table 2). By the end of the final PD, the average score was 21.06, which corresponded with a rating between “somewhat” and “very confident.” Figure 3 is a graph of storyline implementation self-efficacy over time, showing a somewhat linear increase between time points 0 and 3 and a slight but not significant decrease between time points 3 and 4. The 95% confidence intervals around each mean (see Table 4) illustrate that adjacent time points were not always significantly different, but that over time teachers' confidence increased until time point 3 and then plateaued.

[Insert Figure 3]

The mean results for both teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs are encouraging. They show that over time teachers did grow in terms of their beliefs around what good science instruction looks like and their ability to implement OpenSciEd. In addition, the self-efficacy results in particular show the value of engaging in this work iteratively over time; teachers' self-

efficacy initially did not change between the pre-PD survey and the end of PD 1, but it did continue to change for the next year up through round 3. These results support the value of the iterative, long-term approach to science teacher learning taken by the OpenSciEd field test.

Similar to the traditional teaching beliefs models, we then constructed a two-level longitudinal model to explain more nuance than can be seen by averages on their own. The within-person level confirmed that there was a significant increase in storyline implementation self-efficacy over time and that the rate of change of self-efficacy decreased over time. The between-person model helped to identify which teacher characteristics predict differences in self-efficacy (research question 2). Table 7 shows the unconditional and final models for storyline implementation self-efficacy. The HLM model shows that teachers with more previous related PD were more likely to have higher storyline implementation self-efficacy. In addition, teachers who found the PD activities more valuable were likely to show faster increases in self-efficacy over time.

[Insert Table 7]

Once again, the amount of variance explained at each level helps show how well the final model explained variation in storyline implementation self-efficacy. In comparison to the unconditional model, the final model explained 15% of the variance in initial self-efficacy, but less than 1% of the variance in change over time and 4% of the variance within people. This means that there are likely other characteristics that explain differences in storyline implementation self-efficacy.

Summary of Results

Overall, there was a similar pattern of change over time in the survey results related to teachers' traditional beliefs about science teaching and their self-efficacy beliefs about

implementing the OpenSciEd curriculum. Teachers showed a significant decrease in agreement with traditional science teaching statements and significant gains in self-efficacy after initial rounds of PD. In later rounds, these changes leveled off and teachers' teaching and self-efficacy beliefs did not significantly change. The biggest difference between these two measures was that teaching beliefs showed significant changes after round 1 of PD and then plateaued, whereas self-efficacy beliefs did not show significant changes until after round 2. Multilevel models were then used to identify teacher characteristics that predicted differences between teachers in their changes in teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs. Teachers with more experience teaching, more past PD around the NGSS, and who found the PD more valuable were less likely to agree with traditional beliefs about science instruction. Similarly, teachers who had more past PD about the NGSS were more likely to be confident in their OpenSciEd implementation and teachers who found the PD more valuable increased their self-efficacy faster. These models explained 20% or less of the variance in traditional beliefs and implementation self-efficacy, meaning that there are likely other unmeasured variables contributing to these differences between teachers.

Discussion

The study of how the variable of time interacts with PD outcomes is quite popular, but mostly in terms of looking at PD duration, asking if the number of PD contact hours is associated with positive teacher or student learning outcomes (e.g. Blank & de las Alas, 2009; Cohen & Hill, 1998; Crowther & Cannon, 2002; Desimone et al., 2002; Hill & Ball, 2004; Lynch et al., 2019; Yoon et al., 2007). We argue that finding the "correct" number of hours for PD is a pursuit that is both simplistic and likely impossible. It is not simply the existence of many contact hours over a long span of time that supports teacher growth, but rather what actually happens within

those hours, why, and how what happens does or does not support teacher learning and growth (Kennedy, 2016; Lynch et al., 2019). Rather than trying to answer the question of how many hours over what duration of time is most “effective,” we tracked the same group of teachers over time as they engaged in multiple PD workshops and implementation efforts in their own classroom in order to understand the shape of change in their traditional teaching beliefs and storyline implementation self-efficacy over time. In addition, using an HLM model, we identified teacher characteristics associated with these changes.

In this section, we highlight three key takeaways from these analyses and discuss their implications for practice: 1) teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs showed initial changes that leveled out over time; 2) self-efficacy beliefs required more time to change than teaching beliefs; and 3) finding the PD activities valuable was associated with lower traditional teaching beliefs and faster increase in self-efficacy. The section ends with a discussion of limitations of this study and how future research might address these limitations.

Teaching Beliefs and Self-Efficacy Beliefs Change and Level Over Time

After initial rounds of PD, teachers expressed fewer traditional beliefs and higher self-efficacy, but those changes leveled off over time. This finding aligns with other longitudinal studies of teacher learning from multiple rounds of PD over time; for example, Heck and colleagues (2006) found that teachers “pedagogical preparedness” and “content preparedness” increased but leveled off over the course of multiple years of curriculum-based PD. Teachers’ belief systems are complex and change in beliefs over time is rarely linear, meaning beliefs can become more aligned with reform ideas about instruction, regress, and/or plateau over the course of teachers’ careers (Fletcher & Luft, 2011; Pilitsis & Duncan, 2012).

In this group of teachers, on average their teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs plateaued in the second year of the study. This pattern of change has implications for future design of long-term curriculum-based PD as it calls into question the value of repeating similar approaches over time. Teachers with different instructional beliefs respond differently to different kinds of teacher learning activities (Pilitsis & Duncan, 2012). Therefore, a similar phenomenon may have occurred in this case in which the PD workshops were helpful for facilitating initial changes in beliefs but teachers may have needed more differentiated or targeted support as they became more experienced with the curriculum and its implementation in their classroom. More targeted instructional coaching activities such as examining their own students' work or engaging in lesson study might have provided further opportunities to facilitate growth in teachers' teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs rather than continuing to use the same workshop model for PD in later rounds (Gibbons & Cobb, 2017).

Self-Efficacy Beliefs Required More Time to Change than Teaching Beliefs

While the overall shape of change for both teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs were similar, there was a key difference between the two in terms of how many rounds it took to show significant change. Traditional teaching beliefs decreased significantly after one round of PD whereas self-efficacy required two rounds to show significant increases. Multiple studies have shown that PD programs can increase teachers' teaching self-efficacy (Kang et al., 2019; Lo et al., 2014; von Suchodoletz et al., 2018). The results from this study are in line with these previous studies and also demonstrate that self-efficacy beliefs may require more time, iteration, or enactment to change than teaching beliefs.

Teacher learning is not linear, as Guskey (1986) originally proposed, but rather happens in a cyclical process of experience, enactment, and reflection (Clarke & Hollingsworth, 2002).

These cycles are iterative, and teachers' thinking about their instruction and their instructional practice often change together (Kazemi & Hubbard, 2008). It makes sense, therefore, that teachers did not become significantly more confident in their implementation until after they had had an opportunity to teach an OpenSciEd unit. Teachers can express teaching beliefs that do not align with their instructional practice without even noticing that discrepancy (Fletcher & Luft, 2011; Mills et al., 2019). Self-efficacy, on the other hand, is more context-specific, meaning that teachers develop self-efficacy about particular elements of their practice (Jones & Leagon, 2014; Maddux & Gosselin, 2012). For example, one of the items asked teachers' "how confident are you that you can work with students to motivate the next step in investigating a phenomenon, rather than just telling them what they will do next" (see Table 2). This is a particular feature of storyline curricula in which classes jointly establish their next steps even though the likely outcomes have been anticipated by the teacher and curricular materials (Reiser et al., 2021). Given its complexity, teachers may have needed opportunities to attempt this kind of joint navigation in their classrooms and then come back together to reflect with colleagues in a second PD to express more confidence in their ability to do this work. The complexity of these shifts in the instructional model may have a different relationship with time than changes in classroom instruction that are closer to teachers' existing practices (Allen & Penuel, 2015; National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine, 2015). Overall, the results from this study show the value of creating PD opportunities that provide teachers with iterative opportunities to learn about, enact, and then reflect on instructional reforms in order to improve teachers' self-efficacy in implementing and maintaining those reforms over the long-term.

Finding the PD Valuable was Associated with Lower Traditional Teaching Beliefs and Faster Increase in Self-Efficacy

Based on the HLM analysis, three teacher characteristics explained differences in teachers' traditional teaching beliefs and storyline implementation self-efficacy. Those characteristics are past related PD experience, years of teaching experience, and finding the PD activities valuable. Teachers with more PD experience, more teaching experience, and who found the PD activities more valuable were more likely to disagree with the traditional teaching belief statements. Teachers with more past PD experience were more likely to report higher levels of self-efficacy and teachers who found the PD more valuable were more likely to show a faster increase in self-efficacy over time.

Of these variables, teachers' value of the PD is particularly interesting because it is a variable that can be designed for, unlike past PD or teaching experience which are characteristics of teacher participants that cannot be changed. Teacher attitudes about PD can vary widely, and the degree to which teachers find PD valuable impacts their willingness to participate in that PD (Masuda et al., 2013; Torff & Sessions, 2008). This suggests the importance of building trust with PD participants and the importance of providing a rationale for PD experiences.

A key aspect of trust is that it involves being willing to take risks and be vulnerable because of the perceived positive intentions of the party with which one is placing one's trust (Smetana et al., 2016). Well-designed PD involves asking teachers to take intellectual risks in order to push their own thinking forward, so they need to trust the designers and facilitators that those risks will be helpful to their own learning. The data from this study show that teachers who saw that value in the OpenSciEd PD were more likely to quickly increase their self-efficacy, meeting one of the key goals of the PD. Therefore, PD designers should consider how they build

that trust with participants so that it is more likely the participants will meaningfully engage with the work of the PD. For example, connecting the work in PD with teachers' organizational contexts and allowing teachers to consider how to implement ideas from PD in their own context could be a powerful strategy in supporting teachers' buy-in to PD (Allen & Heredia, 2021).

In addition to trusting PD designers and facilitators, another aspect influencing teachers' attitudes towards PD is their motivation for attending (Masuda et al., 2013). Some teachers are intrinsically motivated to attend PD in order to develop their own professional practices and skills, whereas others are more extrinsically motivated by licensure or school requirements (Avidov-Ungar, 2016). Extrinsically motivated teachers may be less likely to see PD as valuable, so less likely to engage with the learning activities and therefore less likely to learn from them (Avidov-Ungar, 2016). This kind of feedback loop has been seen in other contexts of teacher learning. For example, when provided with educative curriculum materials, teachers who saw them only as a source of activities were less likely to learn from them than teachers who saw the materials as a resource to improve their own practice (Marco-Bujosa et al., 2017). Something similar may have occurred in this study. Teachers who saw the PD as valuable were more likely to shift their teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs. While designers cannot change the reasons teachers attend PD, they can help to support intrinsic motivation for participants by pointing out the rationale behind various PD activities and how they might help teachers' learning. For example, teachers who understand that the goal of rehearsing a discussion is to consider and practice their teacher moves in a low-stakes environment (Lampert et al., 2013) might be more likely to engage meaningfully with that activity and therefore come away with more powerful insights into how they might run a similar discussion in their own classroom.

Limitations and Future Work

In this section we discuss three limitations of this study and how future work could address those limitations moving forward. First, the design of data collection necessarily conflated teachers' PD and implementation experiences because surveys were only given after each round of PD but teachers taught OpenSciEd units between each round. Second, the focus of the survey limited our ability to understand how teachers learned about all of the complexities of teaching reform science such as that outlined by the NGSS. Finally, the HLM models explained relatively little of the variance between teachers in terms of changes in teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs. This means the profile of teachers who responded well to the PD is limited and requires more work to better define and understand.

The relationship between teachers' experience in PD and their personal domain of beliefs and ideas is important but far from the only one that influences professional growth (Clarke & Hollingsworth, 2002; Kazemi & Hubbard, 2008). By collecting data on teachers' teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs only after each PD, we were not able to see how changes in these constructs were influenced by teachers' experience teaching as compared to their time in PD. Future work could disentangle this by collecting data on teachers' beliefs during and immediately after implementation as well as after PD to provide a more complex picture of how they change over time.

While we studied teachers' teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs around reform instruction, we could not measure all of the complexity involved in implementing reform-oriented instruction as outlined by the NGSS. For example, a key and complex aspect of the NGSS is the integration of engineering, which is novel and challenging for many teachers (Moore et al., 2015). Although the OpenSciEd curriculum integrates engineering, it is not

uniform across each of the units, with some including it as more of a focus than others (Edelson et al., 2021). In order to account for this heterogeneity, we did not include engineering in the survey items. Therefore, future research could focus on the development of teachers' teaching beliefs and self-efficacy beliefs around engineering and its integration into science, which may show a different pattern than the one described here.

The HLM models showed that teachers with more teaching and PD experience and who better valued the PD were less likely to hold traditional teaching beliefs and more likely to be confident in their ability to implement OpenSciEd. Unfortunately, these models explained relatively little of the variance in these outcomes, meaning this study was unable to dig deeply into which factors beyond time influenced changes in teachers' beliefs. There are certainly other such factors that can help explain how teachers are likely to respond to curriculum-based PD. Qualitative methods, such as case study research, are particularly well suited for identifying and exploring these factors as they can help elucidate complexities of teacher learning and thinking that is obscured by large-scale survey analysis (Yin, 2018). Future work, therefore, should include studying teachers as they engage in a similar series of PD workshops and curriculum implementation to try to explain their unique patterns of learning and identify other characteristics that might explain variation between teachers.

Conclusion

We are in an exciting time in science teacher education. The NGSS and similar state standards call for wide scale change in our approach to science education, and we are just recently beginning to see the release of curriculum materials that truly embrace and implement these exciting reforms (Campbell & Lee, 2021). Pairing high-quality curriculum materials with professional development can be a particularly effective strategy to support teacher learning, but

we still have much to learn about how teachers respond to these structures over time (Lynch et al., 2019; Short & Hirsh, 2020). The findings from this study provide evidence that curriculum-based professional development can help to positively impact teachers' thinking but also that more differentiated or targeted interventions may be needed as teachers become more experienced with the target curriculum. In addition, they demonstrate that while teaching beliefs changed after one round of PD, self-efficacy beliefs required two rounds and an intervening classroom enactment of a new curriculum unit to change. This difference highlights the importance of iterative rounds of learning, enactment, and reflection in PD design (McNeill et al., 2022; Kazemi & Hubbard, 2008). An HLM analysis showed that teachers who have more experience and better value the PD are likely to show quicker changes in self-efficacy and less agreement with traditional teaching beliefs, highlighting the importance of ensuring that teachers find PD activities meaningful and valuable for their learning. True instructional change requires a coherent system of teacher support over time (Loucks-Horsley et al., 2010). As we continue to work towards improving science teaching for all students, we should keep in mind how teachers' ideas change over time so that we can design supports that best meet teachers where they are.

References

- Aguinis, H., Gottfredson, R. K., & Joo, H. (2013). Best-practice recommendations for defining, identifying, and handling outliers. *Organizational Research Methods*, 16(2), 270–301. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428112470848>
- Allen, C. D., & Heredia, S. C. (2021). Reframing organizational contexts from barriers to levers for teacher learning in science education reform. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 32(2), 148–166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2020.1794292>
- Allen, C. D., & Penuel, W. R. (2015). Studying teachers' sensemaking to investigate teachers' responses to professional development focused on new standards. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 66(2), 136–149. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487114560646>
- Avidov-Ungar, O. (2016). A model of professional development: Teachers' perceptions of their professional development. *Teachers and Teaching*, 22(6), 653–669. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2016.1158955>
- Ball, D. L., & Cohen, D. K. (1999). Developing practice, developing practitioners: Toward a practice-based theory of professional education. In L. Darling-Hammond & G. Sykes (Eds.), *Teaching as the learning profession: Handbook of policy and practice* (Vol. 1, pp. 3–22). Jossey-Bass.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. W.H. Freeman.
- Bandura, A. (2006). Guide for constructing self-efficacy scales. In F. Pajares & T. Urdan (Eds.), *Self-efficacy beliefs of adolescents* (pp. 307–337). Information Age Publishing.
- Bang, M., Warren, B., Rosebery, A. S., & Medin, D. (2012). Desettling expectations in science education. *Human Development*, 55, 302–318. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000345322>

- Banilower, E. R., Smith, P. S., Weiss, I. R., Malzahn, K. M., Campbell, K. M., & Weiss, A. M. (2013). Report of the 2012 national survey of science and mathematics education. Horizon Research, Inc. <http://www.horizon-research.com/2012nssme/research-products/reports/technical-report/>
- Blank, R. K., & de las Alas, N. (2009). Effects of teacher professional development on gains in student achievement: How meta analysis provides scientific evidence useful to education leaders. Council of Chief State School Officers. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED544700>
- Bong, M. (2006). Asking the right question: How confident are you that you could successfully perform these tasks? In F. Pajares & T. Urdan (Eds.), *Self-efficacy beliefs of adolescents* (pp. 287–305). Information Age Publishing.
- Borko, H. (2004). Professional development and teacher learning: Mapping the terrain. *Educational Researcher*, 33(8), 3–15. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X033008003>
- Brousseau, B. A., Book, C., & Byers, J. L. (1988). Teacher beliefs and the cultures of teaching. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 39(6), 33–39. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002248718803900607>
- Campbell, T., & Lee, O. (2021). Instructional materials designed for A Framework for K-12 Science Education and the Next Generation Science Standards: An introduction to the special issue. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 32(7), 727–734. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2021.1975359>
- Capps, D. K., Shemwell, J. T., & Young, A. M. (2016). Over reported and misunderstood? A study of teachers' reported enactment and knowledge of inquiry-based science teaching. *International Journal of Science Education*, 38(6), 934–959. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2016.1173261>

- Clarke, D., & Hollingsworth, H. (2002). Elaborating a model of teacher professional growth. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 18(8), 947–967. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(02\)00053-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(02)00053-7)
- Cohen, D. K., & Hill, H. C. (1998). *Instructional policy and classroom performance: The mathematics reform in California (RR-39; CPRE Research Report Series)*. Consortium for Policy Research in Education. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED417942>
- Crawford, B. A. (2007). Learning to teach science as inquiry in the rough and tumble of practice. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 44(4), 613–642. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.20157>
- Crawford, B. A., & Capps, D. K. (2018). Teacher cognition of engaging children in scientific practices. In Y. J. Dori, Z. R. Mevarech, & D. R. Baker (Eds.), *Cognition, Metacognition, and Culture in STEM Education (Vol. 24, pp. 9–32)*. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-66659-4_2
- Crowther, D. T., & Cannon, J. R. (2002). Professional development models: A comparison of duration and effect. In P. A. Rubba, J. A. Rye, W. J. Di Biase, & B. A. Crawford (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2002 annual international conference of the Association for the Education of Teachers in Science (pp. 1397–1411)*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED465639>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute.
- Davis, E. A., & Krajcik, J. S. (2005). Designing educative curriculum materials to promote teacher learning. *Educational Researcher*, 34(3), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X034003003>

- Davis, E. A., Palincsar, A. S., Smith, P. S., Arias, A. M., & Kademian, S. M. (2017). Educative curriculum materials: Uptake, impact, and implications for research and design. *Educational Researcher*, 46(6), 293–304. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X17727502>
- Desimone, L. M. (2009). Improving impact studies of teachers' professional development: Toward better conceptualizations and measures. *Educational Researcher*, 38(3), 181–199. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X08331140>
- Desimone, L. M., Porter, A. C., Garet, M. S., Yoon, K. S., & Birman, B. F. (2002). Effects of professional development on teachers' instruction: Results from a three-year longitudinal study. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 24(2), 81–112. <https://doi.org/10.3102/01623737024002081>
- Edelson, D. C., Reiser, B. J., McNeill, K. L., Mohan, A., Novak, M., Mohan, L., Affolter, R., McGill, T. A. W., Buck Bracey, Z. E., Deutch Noll, J., Kowalski, S. M., Novak, D., Lo, A. S., Landel, C., Krumm, A., Penuel, W. R., Van Horne, K., González-Howard, M., & Suárez, E. (2021). Developing research-based instructional materials to support large-scale transformation of science teaching and learning: The approach of the OpenSciEd middle school program. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 32(7), 780–804. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2021.1877457>
- Field, A. P. (2013). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics* (4th edition). Sage.
- Fletcher, S. S., & Luft, J. A. (2011). Early career secondary science teachers: A longitudinal study of beliefs in relation to field experiences. *Science Education*, 95(6), 1124–1146. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.20450>

- Furtak, E. M., & Penuel, W. R. (2019). Coming to terms: Addressing the persistence of “hands-on” and other reform terminology in the era of science as practice. *Science Education*, 103(1), 167–186. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.21488>
- Garet, M. S., Porter, A. C., Desimone, L., Birman, B. F., & Yoon, K. S. (2001). What makes professional development effective? Results from a national sample of teachers. *American Educational Research Journal*, 38(4), 915–945. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312038004915>
- Gibbons, L. K., & Cobb, P. (2017). Focusing on teacher learning opportunities to identify potentially productive coaching activities. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 68(4), 411–425. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487117702579>
- Greenleaf, C. L., Litman, C., Hanson, T. L., Rosen, R., Boscardin, C. K., Herman, J., Schneider, S. A., Madden, S., & Jones, B. (2011). Integrating literacy and science in biology: Teaching and learning impacts of reading apprenticeship professional development. *American Educational Research Journal*, 48(3), 647–717. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831210384839>
- Greeno, J. G. (1997). On claims that answer the wrong questions. *Educational Researcher*, 26(1), 5–17. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X026001005>
- Guskey, T. R. (1986). Staff development and the process of teacher change. *Educational Researcher*, 15(5), 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X015005005>
- Heck, D. J., Rosenberg, S. L., & Crawford, R. A. (2006). LSC teacher questionnaire study: A longitudinal analysis of data collected between 1997 and 2006. Horizon Research, Inc. <http://www.horizon-research.com/lsc-teacher-questionnaire-study-a-longitudinal-analysis-of-data-collected-between-1997-and-2006>

- Hedeker, D. R., & Gibbons, R. D. (2006). *Longitudinal data analysis*. Wiley-Interscience.
- Hill, H. C., & Ball, D. L. (2004). Learning mathematics for teaching: Results from California's mathematics professional development institutes. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 35(5), 330–351. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30034819>
- Jones, M. G., & Leagon, M. (2014). Science teacher attitudes and beliefs: Reforming practice. In N. G. Lederman & S. K. Abell (Eds.), *Handbook of research on science education* (Vol. 2, pp. 830–847). Routledge.
- Kang, E. J. S., McCarthy, M. J., & Donovan, C. (2019). Elementary teachers' enactment of the NGSS science and engineering practices. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 30(7), 788–814. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2019.1630794>
- Kazemi, E., & Hubbard, A. (2008). New directions for the design and study of professional development: Attending to the coevolution of teachers' participation across contexts. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 59(5), 428–441. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487108324330>
- Kennedy, M. M. (2016). How does professional development improve teaching? Review of *Educational Research*, 86(4), 945–980. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654315626800>
- Kolodner, J. L., Camp, P. J., Crismond, D., Fasse, B., Gray, J., Holbrook, J., Puntambekar, S., & Ryan, M. (2003). Problem-based learning meets case-based reasoning in the middle-school science classroom: Putting Learning by Design(tm) into practice. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 12(4), 495–547. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327809JLS1204_2
- Krajcik, J. S., Blumenfeld, P. C., Marx, R. W., & Soloway, E. (1994). A collaborative model for helping middle grade science teachers learn project-based instruction. *The Elementary School Journal*, 94(5), 483–497. <https://doi.org/10.1086/461779>

- Lampert, M., Franke, M. L., Kazemi, E., Ghouseini, H., Turrou, A. C., Beasley, H., Cunard, A., & Crowe, K. (2013). Keeping it complex: Using rehearsals to support novice teacher learning of ambitious teaching. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 64(3), 226–243.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487112473837>
- Lo, A., Krist, C., Reiser, B., & Novak, M. (2014, March 31). Examining shifts in teachers' understanding of NGSS and their impact on planned instruction. NARST International Conference, Pittsburgh, PA.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315547774_Examining_Shifts_in_Teachers%27_Understanding_of_NGSS_and_their_Impact_on_Planned_Instruction
- Loucks-Horsley, S., Stiles, K. E., Mundry, S., Love, N., & Hewson, P. W. (2010). Designing professional development for teachers of science and mathematics. Corwin Press.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452219103>
- Lowell, B. R., Cherbow, K., & McNeill, K. L. (2021). Redesign or relabel? How a commercial curriculum and its implementation oversimplify key features of the NGSS. *Science Education*, 105(1), 5–32. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.21604>
- Lowell, B. R., & McNeill, K. L. (2020). Using the student hat to push on multiple goals in teacher professional learning. In Proceedings of the 14th International Conference of the Learning Sciences. International Society of the Learning Sciences (ISLS).
<https://repository.isls.org/handle/1/6522>
- Luft, J. A., Firestone, J. B., Wong, S. S., Ortega, I., Adams, K., & Bang, E. (2011). Beginning secondary science teacher induction: A two-year mixed methods study. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 48(10), 1199–1224. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.20444>

- Lynch, K., Hill, H. C., Gonzalez, K. E., & Pollard, C. (2019). Strengthening the research base that informs STEM instructional improvement efforts: A meta-analysis. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 41(3), 260–293.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0162373719849044>
- Maddux, J. E., & Gosselin, J. T. (2012). Self-efficacy. In M. R. Leary & J. P. Tangney (Eds.), *Handbook of self and identity* (2nd ed., pp. 198–224). The Guilford Press.
- Maeng, J. L., Whitworth, B. A., Bell, R. L., & Sterling, D. R. (2020). The effect of professional development on elementary science teachers' understanding, confidence, and classroom implementation of reform-based science instruction. *Science Education*, 104(2), 326–353.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.21562>
- Marco-Bujosa, L. M., McNeill, K. L., González-Howard, M., & Loper, S. (2017). An exploration of teacher learning from an educative reform-oriented science curriculum: Case studies of teacher curriculum use. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 54(2), 141–168. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21340>
- Masuda, A. M., Ebersole, M. M., & Barrett, D. (2013). A qualitative inquiry: Teachers' attitudes and willingness to engage in professional development experiences at different career stages. *Delta Kappa Gamma Bulletin*, 79(2), 6–14.
- McNeill, K. L., Affolter, R., & Reiser, B. J. (2022). Anchoring science professional learning in curriculum materials enactment: Illustrating theories in practice to support teacher learning. In A. Castro Superfine, S. R. Goldman, & M.-L. M. Ko (Eds.), *Teacher learning in changing contexts: Perspectives from the learning sciences* (1st ed., pp. 47–68). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003097112-5>

- McNeill, K. L., González-Howard, M., Katsh-Singer, R., & Loper, S. (2017). Moving beyond pseudoargumentation: Teachers' enactments of an educative science curriculum focused on argumentation. *Science Education*, 101(3), 426–457.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.21274>
- McNeill, K. L., & Knight, A. M. (2013). Teachers' pedagogical content knowledge of scientific argumentation: The impact of professional development on K-12 teachers. *Science Education*, 97(6), 936–972. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.21081>
- McNeill, K. L., & Reiser, B. J. (2018). Open source for opening minds: New OpenSciEd materials support science standards. *The Learning Professional*, 39(6), 44–48.
- Miller, E., Manz, E., Russ, R., Stroupe, D., & Berland, L. (2018). Addressing the epistemic elephant in the room: Epistemic agency and the next generation science standards. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 55(7), 1053–1075.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21459>
- Mills, K., Jass Ketelhut, D., & Gong, X. (2019). Change of teacher beliefs, but not practices, following integration of immersive virtual environment in the classroom. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 57(7), 1786–1811.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633119854034>
- Moore, T. J., Tank, K. M., Glancy, A. W., & Kersten, J. A. (2015). NGSS and the landscape of engineering in K-12 state science standards. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 52(3), 296–318. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21199>
- National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2015). *Science teachers' learning: Enhancing opportunities, creating supportive contexts*. The National Academies Press.
<https://doi.org/10.17226/21836>

- National Research Council. (2012). A framework for K-12 science education: Practices, crosscutting concepts, and core ideas. National Academies Press.
<https://doi.org/10.17226/13165>
- National Research Council. (2015). Guide to Implementing the Next Generation Science Standards. National Academies Press.
- National Science Teaching Association. (n.d.). About the Next Generation Science Standards. Retrieved September 16, 2020, from <http://ngss.nsta.org/About.aspx>
- Nespor, J. (1987). The role of beliefs in the practice of teaching. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 19(4), 317–328. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0022027870190403>
- Netemeyer, R. G., Bearden, W. O., & Sharma, S. (2003). *Scaling procedures: Issues and applications*. Sage Publications.
- NextGenScience. (2022). Design badge materials. <https://www.nextgenscience.org/badgeunits>
- NGSS Lead States. (2013). Next generation science standards: For states, by states. National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/18290>
- Odden, T. O. B., & Russ, R. S. (2019). Defining sensemaking: Bringing clarity to a fragmented theoretical construct. *Science Education*, 103(1), 187–205.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.21452>
- OpenSciEd. (2019). How can a sound make something move?
<https://www.opensciEd.org/instructional-materials/8-2-sound-waves/>
- OpenSciEd. (2020). OpenSciEd Teacher Handbook (Version 3.0).
<https://www.opensciEd.org/teacher-handbook/>
- Osborne, J. (2014). Teaching scientific practices: Meeting the challenge of change. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 25(2), 177–196. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10972-014-9384-1>

- Osborne, J. W. (2010). Data cleaning basics: Best practices in dealing with extreme scores. *Newborn and Infant Nursing Reviews*, 10(1), 37–43.
<https://doi.org/10.1053/j.nainr.2009.12.009>
- Pajares, M. F. (1992). Teachers' beliefs and educational research: Cleaning up a messy construct. *Review of Educational Research*, 62(3), 307–332.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543062003307>
- Penuel, W. R., Fishman, B. J., Yamaguchi, R., & Gallagher, L. P. (2007). What makes professional development effective? Strategies that foster curriculum implementation. *American Educational Research Journal*, 44(4), 921–958.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831207308221>
- Pilitsis, V., & Duncan, R. G. (2012). Changes in belief orientations of preservice teachers and their relation to inquiry activities. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 23(8), 909–936.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10972-012-9303-2>
- Pruitt, S. L. (2014). The Next Generation Science Standards: The features and challenges. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 25(2), 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10972-014-9385-0>
- Raudenbush, S. W., & Bryk, A. S. (2002). *Hierarchical linear models: Applications and data analysis methods* (2nd ed). Sage Publications.
- Raudenbush, S. W., Bryk, A. S., Cheong, Y. F., Congdon, R. T., Jr., & du Toit, M. (2019). HLM 8: Hierarchical linear and nonlinear modeling (8.1.4.14) [Computer software]. Scientific Software International.
- Reiser, B. J., Michaels, S., Moon, J., Bell, T., Dyer, E., Edwards, K. D., McGill, T. A. W., Novak, M., & Park, A. (2017). *Scaling up three-dimensional science learning through*

- teacher-led study groups across a state. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 68(3), 280–298.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487117699598>
- Reiser, B. J., Novak, M., McGill, T. A. W., & Penuel, W. R. (2021). Storyline units: An instructional model to support coherence from the students' perspective. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 32(7), 805–829.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2021.1884784>
- Ricketts, A. (2014). Preservice elementary teachers' ideas about scientific practices. *Science & Education*, 23(10), 2119–2135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11191-014-9709-7>
- Robertson, A. D., Scherr, R., & Hammer, D. (Eds.). (2015). *Responsive Teaching in Science and Mathematics* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315689302>
- Rokeach, M. (1968). *Beliefs, attitudes, and values: A theory of organization and change*. Jossey-Bass.
- Roth, K. J., Wilson, C. D., Taylor, J. A., Stuhlsatz, M. A. M., & Hvidsten, C. (2019). Comparing the Effects of analysis-of-practice and content-based professional development on teacher and student outcomes in science. *American Educational Research Journal*, 56(4), 1217–1253. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831218814759>
- Russ, R. S., & Berland, L. K. (2019). Invented science: A framework for discussing a persistent problem of practice. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 28(3), 279–301.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10508406.2018.1517354>
- Sandholtz, J. H., & Ringstaff, C. (2014). Inspiring instructional change in elementary school science: The relationship between enhanced self-efficacy and teacher practices. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 25(6), 729–751. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10972-014-9393-0>

- Schwarz, C. V., Passmore, C., & Reiser, B. J. (2017). Moving beyond “knowing about” science to making sense of the natural world. In C. V. Schwarz, C. Passmore, & B. J. Reiser (Eds.), *Helping students make sense of the world using next generation science and engineering practices* (pp. 3–21). NSTA Press.
- Short, J., & Hirsh, S. (2020). *The elements: Transforming teaching through curriculum-based professional learning*. Carnegie Corporation of New York.
<https://www.carnegie.org/publications/elements-transforming-teaching-through-curriculum-based-professional-learning/>
- Shulman, L. S. (1987). Knowledge and teaching: Foundations of the new reform. *Harvard Educational Review*, 57(1), 1–23.
- Singer, J. D., & Willett, J. B. (2003). *Applied longitudinal data analysis: Modeling change and event occurrence*. Oxford University Press.
- Smetana, L. K., Wenner, J., Settlage, J., & McCoach, D. B. (2016). Clarifying and capturing “trust” in relation to science education: Dimensions of trustworthiness within schools and associations with equitable student achievement. *Science Education*, 100(1), 78–95.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.21195>
- Smith, J. P., diSessa, A. A., & Roschelle, J. (1994). Misconceptions Reconceived: A Constructivist Analysis of Knowledge in Transition. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 3(2), 115–163.
- Taie, S., & Goldring, R. (2020). Characteristics of public and private elementary and secondary school teachers in the United States: Results from the 2017–18 National Teacher and Principal Survey first look (NCES 2020-142REV). National Center for Education Statistics. <https://nces.ed.gov/pubsearch/pubsinfo.asp?pubid=2020142rev>

- Taylor, J. A., Getty, S. R., Kowalski, S. M., Wilson, C. D., Carlson, J., & Van Scotter, P. (2015). An efficacy trial of research-based curriculum materials with curriculum-based professional development. *American Educational Research Journal*, 52(5), 984–1017. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831215585962>
- Taylor, J. A., Roth, K., Wilson, C. D., Stuhlsatz, M. A. M., & Tipton, E. (2017). The Effect of an analysis-of-practice, videocase-based, teacher professional development program on elementary students' science achievement. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, 10(2), 241–271. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19345747.2016.1147628>
- Torff, B., & Sessions, D. (2008). Factors associated with teachers' attitudes about professional development. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 35(2), 123–133.
- Voet, M., & De Wever, B. (2019). Teachers' adoption of inquiry-based learning activities: The importance of beliefs about education, the self, and the context. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 70(5), 423–440. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487117751399>
- von Suchodoletz, A., Jamil, F. M., Larsen, R. A. A. A., & Hamre, B. K. (2018). Personal and contextual factors associated with growth in preschool teachers' self-efficacy beliefs during a longitudinal professional development study. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 75, 278–289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.07.009>
- Wilson, S. M. (2013). Professional development for science teachers. *Science*, 340(6130), 310–313. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1230725>
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications: Design and methods* (Sixth edition). SAGE.
- Yoon, K. S., Duncan, T., Lee, S. W.-Y., Scarloss, B., & Shapley, K. L. (2007). Reviewing the evidence on how teacher professional development affects student achievement (REL

2007-No. 033; Issues & Answers). US Department of Education, Institute of Education Sciences, National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance, Regional Educational Laboratory Southwest.

<https://ies.ed.gov/ncee/edlabs/projects/project.asp?projectID=70>

Zee, M., & Koomen, H. M. Y. (2016). Teacher self-efficacy and its effects on classroom processes, student academic adjustment, and teacher well-being: A synthesis of 40 years of research. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(4), 981–1015.

<https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654315626801>

Zivic, A., Smith, J. F., Reiser, B. J., Edwards, K. D., Novak, M., & McGill, T. A. W. (2018). Negotiating epistemic agency and target learning goals: Supporting coherence from the students' perspective. International Conference of the Learning Sciences, London, U.K.

Figure 1: The Integrated Model of Professional Growth

Note. From Clarke & Hollingsworth, 2002, figure 3, p.951

Table 1: Summary of OpenSciEd PD Activities

	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4
Round 1: Getting to Know OpenSciEd (June 2018)	Introduction to OpenSciEd, experience an OpenSciEd phenomenon as a student Experience anchoring phenomenon of target unit as a student	Watch classroom video & read vignettes to consider coherence between lessons Construct summary of unit storyline, experience key lessons as a student	Consider talk moves to support discussions, watch classroom video of discussions Plan and rehearse a classroom discussion, experience key lessons as a student	Discuss assessment in OpenSciEd, analyze a sample assessment Analyze assessment and student work from the unit, experience key lessons as a student
Round 2: OpenSciEd Key Instructional Elements (January 2019)	Reflect on experience teaching OpenSciEd, analyze video for key elements of instruction Experience anchoring phenomenon of target unit as a student, construct summary of unit storyline	Analyze classroom video for teacher moves that support key elements of instruction Experience key lessons as a student	---	---

Table 1: Summary of OpenSciEd PD Activities

	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4
Round 3: Supporting Equitable Sensemaking (June 2019)	Analyze video & written scenarios for students' diverse ideas and resources Experience anchoring phenomenon of target unit as a student (half day)	Examine resources and watch classroom video considering how to support equitable classroom culture. Construct summary of unit storyline, experience key lessons as a student	Read discussion planning tool, watch video of a teacher planning & implementing a discussion. Plan and rehearse a classroom discussion, experience key lessons as a student	---
Round 4: Using Assessment to Support Sensemaking (January 2020)	Reflect on and analyze strong assessments Experience anchoring phenomenon of target unit as a student, analyze unit mid-point assessment, construct summary of unit storyline	Analyze student work and discuss how to use assessment data Experience key lessons as a student, review assessments in unit, analyze student work from unit	---	---

Table 2: Teaching and Self-Efficacy Beliefs Items

Teaching Beliefs Items ^a	
<i>For each of the statements below, state the degree to which you agree or disagree.</i>	
1	Teachers should have students do interesting hands-on activities, even if the activities do not relate closely to the concept being studied.
2	Hands-on/laboratory activities should be used primarily to reinforce a science idea that the students have already learned.
3	At the beginning of instruction on a science idea, students should be provided with definitions for new scientific vocabulary that will be used.
4	Teachers should provide students with the outcome of an activity in advance so students know they are on the right track as they do the activity.
5	Students should do hands-on or laboratory activities, even if they do not have opportunities to discuss them as a class.
6	Teachers should explain an idea to students before having them consider evidence that relates to the idea.
7	Students should know what the results of an experiment are supposed to be before they carry it out.
8	When students do a hands-on activity and the data don't come out right, teachers should tell students what they should have found.
9	Students' ideas about a science concept should be deliberately brought to the surface prior to a lesson or unit so that students are aware of their own thinking.
10	It is better for science instruction to focus on ideas in depth, even if that means covering fewer topics
Self-Efficacy Beliefs Items ^b	
<i>How confident are you that you can...</i>	
11	Get students to ask questions at the beginning of a unit that guide the lessons that follow?
12	Work with students to motivate the next step in investigating a phenomenon, rather than just telling them what they will do next?
13	Help students use science practices to figure out pieces of core science ideas?
14	Push students to go deeper to revise their explanatory models of phenomena?
15	Help students put pieces together related to disciplinary core ideas and crosscutting concepts?
^a Answer options: 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = moderately disagree, 3 = slightly disagree, 4 = slightly agree, 5 = moderately agree, 6 = strongly agree.	
^b Answer options: 1 = very unsure, 2 = somewhat unsure, 3 = in the middle, 4 = somewhat confident, 5 = very confident.	

Table 3: Reliability Analysis of Outcome Variables (Cronbach's Alpha)

Factor	Pre-PD	Post-PD1	Post-PD2	Post-PD3	Post-PD4
Traditional teaching beliefs	.759	.818		.833	
Storyline implementation self-efficacy	.880	.835	.872	.823	.861

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for Outcome Variables

Factor	N	Mean	SE	SD	Min- Max	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Traditional teaching beliefs							
Pre-PD	301	22.75	.40	6.97	8-46	21.96	23.54
PD1	207	17.56	.46	6.61	8-48	16.66	18.47
PD3	172	17.64	.56	7.34	8-48	16.54	18.74
Storyline implementation self-efficacy							
Pre-PD	304	19.50	.21	3.69	5-25	19.08	19.92
PD1	209	20.20	.21	3.01	8-25	19.79	20.61
PD2	197	20.78	.23	3.29	9-25	20.31	21.24
PD3	173	21.25	.22	2.87	12-25	20.82	21.68
PD4	162	21.06	.24	3.11	12-25	20.57	21.54

Note. The pre-PD survey was given in May 2018, PD1 in June 2018, PD2 in January 2019, PD3 in June 2019, and PD4 in January 2020

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for Predictor Variables

Variables	N	Mean/%	SE	SD	Min-Max
Value Placed on PD Activities (average)	311	8.45	0.05	0.80	5-9
Gender	302				
Woman		77.5			
Not a woman		22.5			
Race	303				
White		82.2			
Not white		17.8			
Years Teaching	309	12.23	0.47	8.26	0-39
Percent of career teaching middle school science	302	77.11	1.76	30.61	0-100
Minutes per Week Teaching Science	307	271.62	3.63	63.54	90-450
Previous Days of NGSS-Aligned PD	300	6.60	0.63	10.99	0-75
Years Since NGSS Adoption	322	2.71	0.10	1.73	0-5

Figure 2: Mean Traditional Teaching Beliefs over Time

Note. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals

Table 6: Traditional Teaching Beliefs Models

Effect	Traditional Teaching Beliefs	
	Unconditional β (SE β)	Final β (SE β)
Fixed effects		
Status at presurvey (π_{oi})		
Intercept (β_{00})	22.79*** (0.40)	23.24*** (0.41)
Years of teaching experience (β_{01})		-0.09* (0.04)
Previous days of PD (β_{02})		-0.09** (0.03)
Value of PD activities (β_{03})		-1.71*** (0.45)
Linear rate of change (π_{1i})		
Time (β_{10})	-7.02*** (0.58)	-6.94*** (0.59)
Quadratic rate of change (π_{2i})		
Time ² (β_{20})	1.82*** (0.18)	1.81*** (0.19)
Random effects		
Variance components		
Level 1 (σ^2)	17.74 ^a	17.69 ^a
Level 2 intercept (τ_{00})	29.31***	23.56***
Level 2 time (τ_{10})	0.88**	0.92**
Model fit statistics		
Deviance	4389.89	4165.60
Intraclass Correlation Coefficient	0.63	0.57

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

^aThe HLM software does not conduct a hypothesis test for the level 1 variance, so no p-value is reported

Figure 3: Mean Storyline Implementation Self-Efficacy over Time

Note. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals

Table 7: Storyline Implementation Self-Efficacy Models

Effect	Storyline Implementation Self-Efficacy	
	Unconditional β (SE β)	Final β (SE β)
Fixed effects		
Status at presurvey (π_{oi})		
Intercept (β_{00})	19.42*** (0.21)	19.47*** (0.20)
Previous days of PD (β_{01})		0.05*** (0.01)
Linear rate of change (π_{1i})		
Time (β_{10})	0.84*** (0.19)	0.71*** (0.20)
Value of PD activities (β_{11})		0.33*** (0.08)
Quadratic rate of change (π_{2i})		
Time ² (β_{20})	-0.10* (0.05)	-0.10* (0.05)
Random effects		
Variance components		
Level 1 (σ^2)	5.47 ^a	5.27 ^a
Level 2 intercept (τ_{00})	6.68***	5.70***
Level 2 time (τ_{10})	0.10 [†]	0.10*
Model fit statistics		
Deviance	5208.46	4886.99
Intraclass Correlation Coefficient	0.55	0.52

[†]p<.10; *p<.05; **p<.01; ***p<.001

^aThe HLM software does not conduct a hypothesis test for the level 1 variance, so no p-value is reported